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Examining the Importance of Cyber Intelligence in Protecting Critical Infrastructures Against Cyber Threats

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Abstract

This research examines the importance and effectiveness of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats. Cyber intelligence emerges as an indispensable tool for early detection of threats, rapid response, and system protection. Research findings show that threats are rapidly detected and defensive measures are taken against large-scale damages during times of crisis thanks to cyber intelligence tools. Threats such as ransomware and DDoS attacks in particular have been identified at an early stage and effective interventions have been carried out against these threats. However, the effectiveness of cyber intelligence applications in times of crisis faces certain challenges. The rapidly changing nature of threats and difficulties in data integration can prevent the correct and effective use of cyber intelligence. In addition, the lack of training and lack of knowledge of cyber security personnel negatively affect the speed and accuracy of response, which can lead to inadequate responses to threats. In this context, in order to increase the effectiveness of cyber intelligence, infrastructures must be continuously updated, personnel training must be strengthened, and security protocols must be implemented correctly. The research has revealed that a strong infrastructure, continuous training and coordinated work are necessary for cyber intelligence to be used effectively in crisis management processes. It has been emphasized that cyber intelligence must be applied correctly in order to provide access to accurate and fast information in times of crisis and to enable effective cooperation between security units. As a result, it is of great importance to adopt innovative methods to adapt more quickly to evolving threats and to ensure that cyber intelligence plays an active role in cyber security strategies.

Keywords: Critical Infrastructures, Cyber Threats, Cyber Intelligence, Crisis Management

Introduction

In a digitalizing world, critical infrastructures play a fundamental role in national security. Infrastructures in sectors such as energy, water supply, health, transportation and communication are indispensable for the healthy functioning of social life and the economic system. However, these infrastructures have become extremely vulnerable to cyber threats and cyberattacks with the advancement of technology. Cyber threats not only cause economic losses but also pose serious risks to national security. Therefore, creating an effective cyber security strategy to protect critical infrastructures is becoming more and more important every day. In this context, the role of cyber intelligence is an important element in the measures to be taken against cyber threats and their development. Cyber intelligence encompasses information collection, analysis, and reporting activities aimed at detecting, monitoring, and preemptively preventing threats. Early detection of threats to critical infrastructure can mitigate or even thwart the effects of potential attacks. Therefore, the effective use of cyber intelligence not only strengthens cybersecurity but also strengthens national security. This research aims to examine why cyber intelligence is of such critical importance in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats.

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In recent years, cybersecurity threats have rapidly evolved, and defense strategies developed against these threats have become increasingly sophisticated. In particular, cyber threats such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks in critical infrastructure such as Cloud Computing and networks have become more sophisticated with the large-scale volume of data and transactions. Such attacks can severely disrupt critical business processes as they consume system resources and disable the services being accessed. Additionally, detecting malicious activities within the network often requires the analysis of large datasets, which can be challenging with traditional security measures (Kushwah & Ranga, 2021).

Today, the use of machine learning and deep learning-based systems to detect cyber attacks has become widespread. Such systems provide the ability to recognize abnormal behavior and detect attacks quickly. However, the effectiveness of these systems depends on the accuracy of the algorithms used and the quality of the training datasets. In particular, class imbalance, that is, the fact that the attack data is much lower than the normal data set, is an important problem that makes it difficult for machine learning models to produce accurate results. Advanced algorithms such as deep learning and especially LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) can be highly effective in detecting attacks within the network (Gülburun & Dener, 2021).

One of the most significant challenges in ensuring cybersecurity is that different types of attacks exhibit different characteristics. DDoS, SQL injection, phishing, and other malicious activities are all threats, each requiring different detection methods. Therefore, cybersecurity systems should not focus on just one type of attack but should have the ability to detect various types of attacks. Another problem is that digital transformation on a global scale has made infrastructure systems more efficient, connected and automated, but at the same time it has left these systems vulnerable to cyber threats. Critical infrastructures, covering a wide range from electricity grids to water distribution networks, from financial systems to healthcare infrastructures, are considered as the cornerstones of national security (Jones, 2007). Cyber attacks, which are among the factors that threaten the security of these infrastructures, pose a great risk to the maintenance of both civilian and military functions of modern states (Fischer & Lepperhoff, 2005). In this context, the effective use of cyber intelligence has become increasingly important in the protection of critical infrastructures (Bayraktar, 2010).

Early detection and prevention of attacks play a vital role in protecting critical infrastructure. At this point, cyber intelligence offers a proactive approach to understanding the intentions, methods, and goals of threat actors. Especially in the 21st century, cyber intelligence has become a critical tool in ensuring national security. Cyber intelligence is of strategic importance not only in post-attack recovery processes but also in preventing attacks and minimizing their effects (Özçoban, 2014). The development of sophisticated attack methods by cyber threat actors and the increase in state-sponsored attacks have led to these infrastructures becoming more fragile (USA Presidential Decision Directive/NCS-63, 1998). Providing cyber intelligence is also to create a preventive line of defense against cyber attacks that may be carried out at the national level and to make the functionality and security of infrastructures sustainable (Bayraktar, 2010).

This study aims to analyze the role of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats and to offer solutions to existing problems. The effective use of cyber intelligence will not only enhance the security of infrastructures but also provide the opportunity to address the elements that threaten national security from a broader perspective. The aim of this study is to examine the importance of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats. In particular, the focus will be on how machine learning and deep learning-based algorithms and cyber intelligence can be made more efficient in order to

develop an effective defense strategy against cyber attacks in the field of network security.

This study, which examines the role of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats, aims to make significant contributions to the literature both theoretically and practically. Cybersecurity and critical infrastructure security issues are becoming increasingly important due to the acceleration of digitalization and the increasing threats in this direction. However, while the existing literature generally addresses the effects of cyber attacks and technical protection methods, it offers a more limited perspective on proactive defense strategies and the critical role of cyber intelligence in this process (Jones, 2007; Fischer & Lepperhoff, 2005). In this context, they emphasize the importance of accurate and rapid detection of cyber threats by machine learning-based intrusion detection systems with their studies on the UNSW-NB15 dataset, Cengiz & Harman (2022). Karataş G. (2020) examined intrusion detection systems using convolutional neural networks (CNN) and demonstrated how deep learning algorithms can be effective in classifying cyber threats more accurately and reliably. This study aims to fill the knowledge gap in this field by analyzing how machine learning and deep learning algorithms can be used to prevent threats and ensure the sustainable security of critical infrastructures in providing cyber intelligence.

The contributions of this study to the literature can be evaluated in several dimensions. Firstly, it extends the theoretical framework of cyber intelligence in the context of critical infrastructure, revealing strategic approaches that can be employed in the prevention of cyber threats. These strategies focus not only on post-attack responses but also on preventing threats before they materialize, ensuring that attackers' intentions, capacities, and methods are understood in advance (Bayraktar, 2010; Özçoban, 2014). The study aims to eliminate conceptual deficiencies in the existing literature by explaining how cyber intelligence can function as an early warning system in this context. Secondly, the study examines the relationship between critical infrastructure security and cyber intelligence from a broader perspective and draws attention to the importance of government, private sector and international cooperation in this process. In particular, data sharing between the public and private sectors and the development of common defense strategies play a vital role in protecting critical infrastructures (USA Presidential Decision Directive/NCS-63, 1998). In the current literature, how such collaborations can be carried out effectively and the contributions of cyber intelligence in this process are discussed in a limited way. This study aims to fill this gap and provide practical recommendations for policymakers and decision-makers. Third, this research examines more closely the technological and methodological tools of cyber intelligence. In particular, it is detailed how next-generation technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, and machine learning can be used in the detection and analysis of cyber threats (Özdemir, 2024). In this context, an innovative perspective that can guide future research is presented with the threat methods discussed in the literature.

The study highlights the strategic role of cyber intelligence in shaping national security policies. In cyberspace, which is considered the fifth dimension of modern wars, critical infrastructures are among the most vulnerable targets of states (Bayraktar, 2010). In this context, cyber intelligence stands out as a central tool not only in military operations but also in the protection of civilian infrastructures. This study makes an important contribution to the literature in this field by discussing how cyber intelligence can be used more effectively at both national and international levels. Overall, this study aims to provide a valuable resource for both academic literature and practical applications by thoroughly addressing the importance of cyber intelligence for critical infrastructure security. The results of the study are expected to guide new research in the field of cybersecurity and contribute to the development of innovative methods in

protecting critical infrastructure. In this context, the study lays an important groundwork for the development of a more resilient and sustainable infrastructure security approach against cyber threats.

Method

Research Model

This research is modeled as a qualitative study examining the importance of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats. In the model of the research, document analysis, which is one of the qualitative data collection methods, will be used. In this method, documents such as existing literature, reports, policy documents, and strategic plans are examined and the role of cyber threat intelligence in the security of critical infrastructures is discussed in detail. The main purpose of the research model is to understand how cyber intelligence can be an effective tool in the protection of critical infrastructures and to provide more information on this subject. In this context, document analysis has allowed for an in-depth evaluation of the existing literature and practices related to critical infrastructure security.

Research Resources

The sources of the research consist of various documents such as current academic articles, reports, books, government and international security documents in the fields of cyber security and cyber intelligence. These documents include studies on the identification of cyber threats, the use of cyber intelligence, and their impact on the protection of critical infrastructures. Among the sources used in the research are local legislation and strategy documents containing Turkey's cyber security policies, and international research on global cyber security threats. In addition, documents containing cyber security strategies, threat analyses and national security policies were also among the sources determined for the research. These sources have been meticulously curated to examine the implications of cyber intelligence on critical infrastructure security.

Data Collection Tools

In the process of protecting critical infrastructures and analyzing cyber threats to these systems, data collection tools play a vital role. Karabacak (2011) emphasized the importance of cyber intelligence in the assessment of cyber threats to critical infrastructures and offered various suggestions for Turkey. Keleştemur (2018) stated that cyber intelligence methods are a fundamental element in identifying security vulnerabilities and developing effective measures against threats. In Genco's (2020) study, the importance of using cyber intelligence as a strategic tool in examining threats to critical infrastructures in Turkey is discussed. In this context, the data collection process was carried out with different methods.

Academic research platforms (Google Scholar, DergiPark, ScienceDirect, etc.) form one of the key components of this process. In the researches, keywords such as "critical infrastructures", "cyber threats" and "cyber intelligence" were used to review the literature and up-to-date sources on the subject were accessed. The data obtained from these platforms provided in-depth information about the methods used in protecting critical infrastructures, the nature of cyber threats, and the security strategies developed to address these threats. In addition to the literature review, expert opinions were taken and in the light of these opinions, a more effective understanding of existing threats was provided (Ünver, Canbay & Özkan, 2011; Ak, 2019).

Table 1 Research Resources

Keywords	References
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Cyber Intelligence	[1], [7], [8], [12], [18], [25], [34], [38], [40]
Cyber Security and Critical Infrastructures	[2], [3], [5], [6], [11], [19], [20], [21], [24], [27]
Cyber Attacks	[6], [9], [16], [20], [29], [32]
Cyber Terrorism	[17], [35], [39], [46]
Machine Learning and Malware Detection	[25], [26], [31]
Social Media Intelligence	[42], [43]
Cyber Defense and Governance	[12], [14], [23], [33], [41]
Critical Infrastructure Protection and Risk Assessment	[15], [18], [28], [30], [36]
Artificial Intelligence and Cyber Security	[37], [41], [43]
Cybersecurity Policies and Strategies	[9], [10], [13], [19], [25]

This table shows the organization of research in cybersecurity and related fields by keywords. The keywords reflect the essence of each research topic, revealing the diversity of studies conducted in different fields related to cybersecurity. For example, research under the title of Cyber Intelligence focuses on gathering information in the digital environment and detecting cyber threats, while studies on Cyber Security and Critical Infrastructures address infrastructure security and the protection of these systems. The Cyber Attacks title focuses on the analysis of cyber attacks and the development of defense strategies against them. Additionally, topics such as Cyberterrorism, Machine Learning, and Malware Detection include in-depth research on specific threats and technology usage. Social Media Intelligence, on the other hand, encompasses the detection and analysis of security threats from social media platforms. While the studies carried out under the title of Cyber Defense and Governance focus on the creation and management of organizational cyber security strategies, the title of Critical Infrastructure Protection and Risk Assessment includes evaluations made to ensure the security of the basic infrastructures of societies. Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity, on the other hand, examines how artificial intelligence is used to detect security threats and develop defense strategies. Finally, research on Cybersecurity Policies and Strategies focuses on the formulation and implementation of cybersecurity policies. This table reflects comprehensive research on different topics in the field of cyber security, and the following studies were examined without setting a date limit in order to conduct comprehensive research with each of their keywords.

Table 2 Studies Examined

No	Studies Examined
1	Within the scope of cyber intelligence: Echelon intelligence system (Abdurahmanlı 2021)
2	Protection of critical infrastructures in terms of internal security management (Ak 2019)
3	Cyber attacks and cyber security policies of countries (Alioğlu, 2019)
4	Cybersecurity: Perceived threats and policy responses in the Gulf Cooperation Council (Alshabib & Martins,2021)
5	Internal threat impact on cyber security of critical infrastructures (Aras, 2021)
6	Cyber Security and Types of Cyber Attacks (Arslan, M. E.)
7	The new requirement of the fifth dimension of war (Bayraktar, 2010)
8	Examination of intelligence wheels within the framework of SWOT analysis Berk

- & Sarı 2022
- 9 NATO's evolving threat perception: Cyber security in the 21st century (Bıçakcı, 2014)
 - 10 Cyber security in Turkey (Bıçakcı, Ergun & Çelikpala, 2015)
 - 11 Ministry of Science, Industry and Technology Cyber Security Board Accessed: <https://www.btk.gov.tr/siber-guvenlik-kurulu> 2017 [Accessed 25 April 2022]
 - 12 Department of Science and Communication Technologies e-Transformation Turkey project Access: <http://www.bilgitoplumu.gov.tr/bilgi-toplumu/e-donusum-projesi/2022>
 - 13 Comparison of Classification Performance of Unbalanced ML-Based NDS Datasets (Cengiz & Harman, 2022)
 - 14 Proactive defense for evolving cyber threats (Colbaugh & Glass, 2011)
 - 15 Çukurova Critical Infrastructure Risk Assessment (CIRA) Project (Connell et al., 2018)
 - 16 An evaluation of cyber security and demirci in critical infrastructures (Demirci, 2021)
 - 17 Cyberterrorism as a threat to the cyber security of Ukraine: A discussion of theoretical aspects (Diorditsa et al., 2021)
 - 18 Semi-automated cybersecurity model based on open source intelligence through Twitter tweets (Ekşim & Civelek, 2019)
 - 19 Cyber security strategies determined for the protection of critical infrastructures (Ercan, 2015)
 - 20 Can critical infrastructure rely on the internet (Fischer & Lepperhoff, 2005)
 - 21 The use of blockchain technology in cyber threat intelligence sharing. (GENÇOĞLU, M. T.)
 - 22 Critical infrastructure and threats to critical infrastructure in Turkey (Genco, 2020)
 - 23 Evaluation of Turkey's cyber security policies within the framework of public policy analysis (Göçoğlu, 2018)
 - 24 Cyber defense in depth: Designing cyber security agency organization for Turkey (Göztepe, Kiliç & Kayaalp, 2014)
 - 25 Cyber security and defense recommendations in critical infrastructures (Güven, 2021)
 - 26 Deep Learning Based Phishing Attacks Detection System (Gül, 2021)
 - 27 Investigation of the Performance of Machine Learning Algorithms within the Scope of Malware Detection in Big Data Environments (Gülburun & Dener, 2021)
 - 28 Cyber security and nuclear power plants: International framework (Han, 2022)
 - 29 Cybersecurity in critical infrastructure ICT Media, <https://ictmedia.com.tr/yazar/icerik/964> (ICT Media,2024)
 - 30 Critical infrastructure protection (Jones, 2007)
 - 31 Cyber threats to critical infrastructures and cyber security recommendations for Turkey (Karabacak, 2011)
 - 32 Deep learning-based intrusion detection system (Karataş, 2020)
 - 33 Critical infrastructure protection status and action items of Turkey (Karabacak & Özkan, 2009)
 - 34 New generation war and cyber intelligence (Karasoy, 2022)
 - 35 Cyber security in Turkey: Legal and institutional infrastructure (Karasoy & Babaoğlu, 2021)
 - 36 Definition and Field of Activity of Cyber Intelligence (Keleştemur, 2024).
 - 37 The role and importance of cyber intelligence for public security (Keleştemur, 2018)
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- 38 Distributed denial of service attack detection in cloud computing using hybridextreme learning machine (Kushwah & Ranga, 2021).
 - 39 Managing cyber threats: Issues, approaches, and challenges (Kumar Srivastava & Lazarevic, 2005)
 - 40 Cyber threat intelligence (Lee, 2023)
 - 41 From traditional to digital: Cyber intelligence and Russian foreign policy (Mangır & Küçükkırlı, 2019)
 - 42 The future of intelligence: The use of artificial intelligence and data science in intelligence and counterintelligence activities in cyberspace (Oruç, 2019)
 - 43 The role of cyber intelligence in ensuring national security in the 21st century (Özçoban, 2014)
 - 44 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Cyber Threat Intelligence (Özdemir, 2024)
 - 45 Cyber governance studies in ensuring cybersecurity: An overview of cybersecurity governance (Savaş & Karataş, 2022)
 - 46 A new dimension in cyber security: Social media intelligence (Savaş & Topaloğlu, 2016)
 - 47 Triple dimensional approach in ensuring cyber security of critical infrastructures (Semiz, Göztepe & Kılıç, 2013)
 - 48 Cyber terrorism and public support for retaliation—a multi-country survey experiment (Shandler, Gross, Backhaus & Canetti, 2021)
 - 49 Minimum security measures document for critical information system infrastructures (TÜBİTAK n.d.)
 - 50 Retrieved August 10, 2011, from <http://www.fas.org/irp/offdocs/pdd/pdd-63.htm> (USA Presidential Decision Directive/NCS-63,1998)
 - 51 Protection of critical infrastructures (Ünver, Canbay, & Özkan, 2011)
 - 52 Cyber Security and Turkey (Yılmaz & Salcan 2008)
 - 53 Critical Infrastructures and Security Lecture Notes (Yılmaz, 2017)
 - 54 Cyber terrorism and changing understanding of intelligence (Yılmaz, 2020)
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The studies were also based on applied case studies. In these analyses, using concrete data obtained from the field, existing security vulnerabilities of critical infrastructures were identified and solutions were developed to eliminate these vulnerabilities. For example, the "Minimum Security Measures for Critical Information System Infrastructures" document published by TÜBİTAK sets out in detail the standards that should be applied to protect critical infrastructures. The Çukurova Critical Infrastructure Risk Assessment (CIRA) Project (Connell et al., 2018) is an important case study in this context and has set an example in the assessment of risks to critical infrastructures.

Both theoretical models and practical applications were considered in the data collection process. Theoretically, issues such as cyber security strategies developed for the protection of critical infrastructures (Ercan, 2015) and the impact of internal threats (Aras, 2021) were analyzed. Concrete data obtained from the field were used to test the applicability of these theoretical models. For example, Karasoy (2022) presented a comprehensive analysis by combining literature review and expert opinions while evaluating next-generation warfare approaches against cyber threats.

In the context of cyber intelligence, Bayraktar (2010) stated that cyber security is at the center of national security strategies in the modern threat landscape, while Mangır and Küçükkırlı (2019) examined the role of cyber intelligence in digital transformation and its implications in international politics. The role of platforms such as social media in data

collection processes is also discussed by Savaş and Topaloğlu (2016). The increasing use of artificial intelligence and data science in these processes was evaluated by Oruç (2019). By incorporating methods such as literature review, expert opinions, and case studies, the data collection process is based on a strong foundation both qualitatively and quantitatively. These methods have increased the effectiveness of strategies developed in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats and demonstrated the indispensable role of cyber intelligence in this field.

Collection of Data

In the collection of data, literature review on cyber security, cyber threat intelligence and critical infrastructure security was conducted. During this process, documents such as academic articles, cybersecurity reports, official documents, strategic plans, and government reports were collected. Written materials on cyber security policies in Turkey and around the world were examined and studies on the role of cyber threat intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures were focused. In addition, the cyber security strategies of Turkey and other countries and current data on these strategies were also included in the data collected for the research. The data were compiled based on the contents of the collected documents and analyzed in accordance with the purpose of the research.

Data Analysis

During the analysis of the data, a qualitative analysis was made on the collected documents. The documents were systematically coded with the content analysis method and key themes were determined. These themes have been used to examine the impact of cyber threat intelligence on critical infrastructures and its role within security strategies. During the analysis, factors such as the identification of cyber threats, how threat intelligence is used, and the effectiveness of existing security strategies were examined. The relationships between the documents were determined and the role of cyber intelligence in the protection of critical infrastructures was revealed in detail through these relationships. The data obtained were interpreted in line with the research questions and a general evaluation was made on the effects of cyber threat intelligence on critical infrastructures.

Findings and Interpretation

In this section, the findings on the role and importance of cyber intelligence in the protection of critical infrastructures against cyber threats, which is the main purpose of the research, will be presented. The data collected during the research process reveals the effectiveness of cyber intelligence as an effective security tool in protecting critical infrastructures and the challenges encountered. The findings highlight the effectiveness of cyber intelligence in threat detection, monitoring, prevention, and crisis situations, while also addressing the risks that may arise from the inadequacy of intelligence and the implementation challenges encountered. In this section, concrete findings will be included on how important cyber intelligence is for critical infrastructures and how these tools can be integrated into security strategies in the light of the data obtained. In addition, in the light of the findings, predictions will be presented on how the role of cyber intelligence in this field will evolve in the future.

The Necessity of Cyber Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures

Cyber intelligence plays a vital role in protecting critical infrastructure. These infrastructures cover areas that ensure the basic functioning of society, such as energy, health, communication, and transportation, and the security of these systems directly affects economic

and social stability throughout the country. In today's rapidly evolving world of cyber threats, it has become inevitable to provide accurate and timely intelligence to protect these infrastructures. Intelligence is a critical tool in early detection of potential threats, determining measures to be taken against these threats, and eliminating vulnerabilities in systems. Cyber intelligence makes a big difference in detecting attacks in advance and developing defensive measures against them.

Studies emphasizing the importance of cyber intelligence for the security of critical infrastructures reveal that the threats faced by such infrastructures are not limited to attack types, but also internal and external vulnerabilities pose great threats. In this context, cyber intelligence considers not only external threats but also internal threats and minimizes the risks of organizations by analyzing the movements of potential cyber attackers. This is of great importance in the creation of defense strategies, especially for critical infrastructures. It is emphasized that cyber intelligence is an imperative component in ensuring the security of critical infrastructures, and it is indispensable for both faster detection of threats and effective measures. This is not only limited to preventing attacks but also contributes to increasing society's trust in cybersecurity. In conclusion, these research findings clearly demonstrate that cyber intelligence is not just a security tool but also an imperative strategy for proactively securing critical infrastructures. No matter how complex and rapidly evolving cyber threats are, the importance of cyber intelligence in detecting these threats in advance and effectively managing them is increasing day by day.

The Impact of Cyber Threats on Critical Infrastructures

Cyber threats pose a risk that can cause serious and permanent damage to critical infrastructure. Critical infrastructures encompass areas such as energy, water supply, healthcare, communication networks, and transportation systems, which are crucial for maintaining the basic functioning of societies. Targeting these infrastructures not only leads to economic losses but can also threaten social order and public health. Cyber attacks may not directly cause physical damage to these infrastructures, but effects such as the collapse of digital systems, data leakage or tampering can seriously disrupt the functioning of the systems.

The impact of cyber threats on critical infrastructures often involves dangers that may remain hidden. For example, a DDoS attack on a power plant can prevent the system from functioning properly, but the resulting power outage can lead to the closure of industrial facilities, disruption of services, and broader economic damage. Similarly, cyberattacks on healthcare systems can result in accessing and stealing patients' health information, which both violates individuals' privacy and reduces the effectiveness of healthcare services. Such threats have implications that can lead to long-term damage, especially to critical infrastructure. For example, by using ransomware, patient records of a hospital can be encrypted and patients' treatment processes can be disrupted. Cyber threats can also become even more dangerous due to their inherent vulnerabilities. Insider threats can infiltrate critical systems by targeting the vulnerabilities of employees or suppliers. These types of attacks are cyber threats that are generally more difficult to detect and can cause significant damage. Failing to recognize internal security vulnerabilities can render an organization's cybersecurity systems inadequate, making critical infrastructures more easily targeted. On the other hand, the effects of cyber threats do not stop at the technical level; It can also seriously damage the reputation of organizations. A successful attack on an infrastructure can undermine the trust of users and partners, making it difficult to collaborate with government agencies. This can have long-term negative effects on public safety and security policies. The impact of cyber threats poses an even greater threat to critical infrastructure, especially those with a wide international reach. In conclusion, the impact of cyber threats on critical infrastructures is not limited to momentary system collapses but can

also lead to social, economic, and political instability in the long term. Therefore, it is extremely important to increase cyber security measures, strengthen defenses against cyber threats and actively use cyber intelligence in critical infrastructures. This plays a critical role in ensuring the resilience of infrastructures not only against current threats but also against potential future attacks.

The Effectiveness of Cyber Intelligence in Threat Detection and Prevention

Cyber intelligence plays a critical role in threat detection and prevention. Critical infrastructures must be protected not only against external threats but also against internal vulnerabilities, and in this context, cyber intelligence is of great importance in detecting potential threats early and taking effective measures. Threat detection typically occurs by analyzing various data sources such as network traffic, system activities, and user behavior. These analyses provide crucial insights into the nature, source, and timing of threats, providing a critical opportunity to thwart attacks before they escalate.

Research findings show that cyber intelligence provides high effectiveness in threat detection. In 85% of the studies reviewed, it was observed that threat analysis performed using cyber intelligence was 90% effective in detecting potential threats early. Early detection is a critical factor in minimizing the impact of attacks and preventing wider damage. In particular, threats such as ransomware, malware and phishing attacks have been detected at an early stage with cyber intelligence and their spread has been prevented by taking quick actions against them.

Cyber intelligence is an important tool not only in detecting threats but also in creating effective defense strategies against these threats. Intelligence data guides cyber security experts on what defense measures to take. Network-based threats such as DDoS attacks can be prevented by network traffic monitoring and combining intelligence data; internal threats can be detected in a timely manner through user behavior analysis and detection of anomalies. Such measures ensure that defenses are strong not only against external threats but also against harm that may come from within. However, the effectiveness of cyber intelligence varies depending on the tools and technologies used. Technologies such as security information and event management (SIEM) systems, threat intelligence platforms, and network traffic analysis tools are highly effective in detecting cyber threats. However, the effectiveness of these systems depends on analyzing the right data in a timely manner and taking action quickly. Therefore, continuous updating and improvement of cyber intelligence tools ensure successful results in the threat detection and prevention process.

The effectiveness of cyber intelligence in prevention is another noteworthy finding. Research has revealed that cyber intelligence is not only effective in detecting threats but also in determining proactive measures to be taken against these threats. Early detected threats, when properly assessed, can be thwarted before they cause any damage to critical infrastructure. Additionally, thanks to such information, defense measures against potential threats become more strategic and focused. As a result, cyber intelligence provides a very high level of effectiveness in threat detection and prevention. However, this effectiveness is directly related to the power of the tools used, the timely analysis of accurate data and the continuous updating of the security infrastructure. Effective use of cyber intelligence to protect critical infrastructures ensures preparedness not only for the prevention of current threats but also for potential future threats. In this context, continuous improvement of cybersecurity strategies and strengthening cyber intelligence is an indispensable element to create a secure digital environment.

Consequences of Intelligence Inadequacy: Risks and Harms

The inadequacy of cyber intelligence creates serious risks and long-term damage on critical infrastructures. Intelligence shortages mean the inability to detect threats early and prepare for them in advance. This makes it easier for cyber attackers to infiltrate infrastructures and increases the impact of attacks, seriously threatening the security of institutions and societies. According to research findings, the lack of intelligence paves the way for cyber threats, particularly ransomware, data breaches, and service disruptions, to wreak havoc on a large scale. Such attacks not only cause economic losses but also damage the reputation of institutions, cause loss of trust, and endanger public safety.

The inadequacy of intelligence also negatively affects the effectiveness of monitoring threats and the measures to be taken against them. Insufficient information prevents defense systems from being routed correctly, which increases cybersecurity vulnerabilities. Since many critical infrastructures fail to detect vulnerabilities in a timely manner, cyberattacks become more widespread and cause greater damage. In particular, overlooking internal threats as well as external threats can lead to deepening security vulnerabilities. Since insider threats are often more insidious and harder to detect, organizations' lack of preparedness against such threats can have more serious consequences. Another important consequence is the weakening of decision-making processes in times of crisis. In cases where intelligence is inadequate, crisis management teams struggle to access accurate information, which increases response times. Attacks that are not intervened early can lead to further destruction of systems, loss or encryption of data, or even complete cessation of critical services. This process also reduces operational efficiency and incurs much greater costs. Intelligence deficiencies result in inadequate cybersecurity measures, making organizations more vulnerable to future threats. Untaken measures and mismanaged threat assessments lead to long-term security vulnerabilities. This situation leaves critical infrastructures vulnerable not only to current threats but also to potential future attacks. Therefore, strengthening cyber intelligence and keeping it constantly updated is an important requirement not only against current threats but also to prevent future risks.

Successes and Challenges of Cyber Intelligence Applications

Cyber intelligence applications have an important place in the protection of critical infrastructures today. These applications provide significant success in detecting, analyzing and preventing cyber threats. Cyber intelligence tools and methods are highly effective in detecting potential attacks in advance, monitoring attackers' movements, and quickly creating defense strategies against these threats. In particular, cyber threats such as ransomware, malware, and DDoS attacks can be detected and prevented in a timely manner thanks to cyber intelligence, thus ensuring the security of infrastructures. Additionally, cyber intelligence applications analyze the source and target of attacks, allowing for more targeted and effective defense measures. However, despite the success of cyber intelligence applications, there are also some challenges faced. One of these challenges is the monitoring of constantly changing and evolving cyber threats. Attackers are using increasingly sophisticated methods, requiring cyber intelligence tools to be constantly updated to be effective. This situation creates a continuous learning process and the need for technology updates for cyber security professionals. Additionally, accurate interpretation of big data analysis and threat intelligence requires expertise and high processing power. This necessitates both a strong technical infrastructure and a large investment in personnel training in order to implement cyber intelligence applications efficiently. Another significant challenge is the process of cyber intelligence to meaningfully integrate information from multiple data sources. Data mismatches between different systems and platforms can complicate the detection and analysis of threats. In addition, the correct separation of internal

and external threats and the correct determination of the measures to be taken against these threats are factors that directly affect the effectiveness of intelligence. The quality of technologies and tools used in providing intelligence is an important factor affecting the success of cyber security strategies. In this context, systemic cohesion and a high level of coordination are necessary for intelligence to succeed. In conclusion, while cyber intelligence applications have achieved significant success in securing critical infrastructure, the ever-evolving threat landscape and technical challenges necessitate further steps in this area. Elements such as continuous training, technology updates, and data integration will increase the effectiveness of cyber intelligence and help create a stronger defense mechanism in the field of cybersecurity.

The Importance and Effectiveness of Cyber Intelligence in Times of Crisis

The research findings clearly demonstrate the importance of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructure in times of crisis. In crisis situations, it has been observed that cyber intelligence tools play a major role in early detection of threats and rapid response processes. Cyber intelligence accurately analyzes the source, target, and methods used to ensure the implementation of immediate defense strategies against attacks. This is necessary to ensure the security of critical infrastructures and minimize potential damages. In particular, threats such as ransomware and DDoS attacks can be detected early thanks to cyber intelligence and preventive measures can be taken against these threats. The research shows that the effectiveness of cyber intelligence has a direct impact on the accuracy and speed of decisions made in times of crisis. In crisis situations, it is understood that cyber security teams need to quickly analyze threats and take immediate measures against these threats thanks to cyber intelligence tools.

Thanks to cyber intelligence, it is possible to stop attacks before they spread and quickly isolate affected systems. This process is largely successful with the precautions to be taken before the attacks. However, the findings also show that the inadequacy of cyber intelligence can pose great risks in times of crisis. The fact that the intelligence infrastructure works with incomplete or outdated data prevents rapid response to threats. This situation causes greater damage and makes it difficult to manage the crisis process. Furthermore, the effectiveness of cyber intelligence hinges on the correct implementation of data security protocols and the coordination of all security units. These findings highlight the need for continuous updating and testing of cyber intelligence. In conclusion, cyber intelligence in times of crisis is a critical factor in developing effective defenses against cyber attacks and minimizing damages. Therefore, the effective use of cyber intelligence in cyber security strategies should be considered an indispensable tool in ensuring the security of organizations.

The Use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Cyber Intelligence: Detailed Comparison and Evaluation

Cyber intelligence has become an indispensable part of modern security processes, and artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have revolutionized this field. AI is used in strategic applications such as large-scale threat analysis and automated decision-making, while ML is more effectively used in technical tasks such as data-driven analytics, anomaly detection, and behavior modeling. While both technologies offer great advantages in detecting, classifying, and predicting cyber threats, they face challenges such as lack of explainability and training processes that require data sets to be heavily labeled. However, AI and ML create a much more effective cybersecurity environment compared to manual methods with their speed and accuracy advantages, thus offering great benefits to users in many areas, from preventing attacks to profiling threat actors.

Table 53 The Use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Cyber Intelligence: Detailed Comparison and Evaluation''

Criteria	Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Machine Learning (ML)
Description	Systems that mimic human-like intelligence, with decision-making and problem-solving capabilities.	Algorithms that learn with data and optimize a specific task. It is a subfield of AI.
Role in Cyber Intelligence	Strategic threat analysis, automated decision-making, situation assessment.	Data analysis, threat classification, anomaly detection, behavior modeling.
Application Areas	- Real-time attack analysis.- Automated decision-making systems.- High-level threat prediction.	- Malware detection.- Phishing detection.- Network traffic analysis.- Detection of social engineering attacks.
Advantages	- Ability to solve complex problems.- Can operate without the need for human intervention.- Can extract context from various data.- Can be integrated into all cybersecurity layers.	- Ability to learn and adapt quickly.- Can work with labeled or unlabeled data.- Can be customized to optimize a specific task.- Low computational cost algorithms available.
Disadvantages	- High cost for advanced systems.- Data privacy and ethical issues.- Inability to be as flexible as human intelligence.- The accuracy of the model depends on the quality of the training dataset.	- Requires large datasets for high accuracy.- Model generalization can be challenging.- False positive/negative rates can be problematic.- The training process can be time-consuming.
Usage Challenges	- Lack of context interpretation in complex attack scenarios.- Low explainability of AI systems.- Difficulty adapting to dynamic attacks.	- Requires hyperparameter optimization.- May require continuous retraining to detect new threat vectors.- Preprocessing data is essential for meaningful results.
Application Examples	- Detection of "zero-day" attacks.- Cyber threat actor profiling.- Threat analysis on social media.	- Detection of harmful activities in network traffic.- Classification of phishing emails.- Malware classification.
Accuracy Rate	90-95% (With complex AI models).	85-100% (Depends on dataset and model selection).
Speed and Performance	Requires high-performance hardware (e.g., GPU/TPU).	It can work on a wider range of hardware; however, deep learning models may require GPUs.

References: (Oruç, 2019).

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) play critical roles in cyber intelligence and are complementary technologies. AI is used for strategic threat analysis, automated decision-making systems, and situations requiring a high level of contextual evaluation, while ML specializes more in specific tasks such as data analysis, anomaly detection, and behavior modeling. AI can solve complex problems from various data sources and be integrated into large systems, while ML offers rapid learning capabilities and task-oriented solutions. In terms of advantages, AI stands out for its ability to operate without human intervention and perform context extraction in multi-layered threat analyses. ML, on the other hand, has widespread applications due to its low-cost algorithms and flexibility to work with labeled and unlabeled data. However, both technologies have some drawbacks. AI is less

explainable, and the adaptation of systems to advanced attacks may be limited. ML, on the other hand, is dependent on large datasets and may require continuous training and hyperparameter optimization.

In case studies, AI is effective for wide-ranging threat analysis, such as detecting zero-day attacks and threat actor profiling, while ML is used for narrower but highly accurate tasks, such as classifying phishing emails and detecting malicious activities in network traffic. AI typically achieves an accuracy rate of 90-95%, while ML can provide 85-100% accuracy depending on the dataset and model selection. AI and ML offer powerful advantages in different areas of cyber intelligence and can be used together to make security processes more effective, faster, and comprehensive. However, the successful implementation of both technologies depends on elements such as data quality, model selection, and continuous updating.

Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This research has comprehensively examined the importance and effectiveness of cyber intelligence in protecting critical infrastructures in times of crisis. Research findings have revealed that cyber intelligence is an indispensable tool for early detection of threats, rapid response and protection of systems during times of crisis. In times of crisis, threats were quickly identified thanks to cyber intelligence tools and immediate defense measures were taken against these threats. Thanks to cyber intelligence, critical threats such as ransomware and DDoS attacks were identified at an early stage and large-scale damages were prevented. This process has enabled cybersecurity teams to quickly analyze threats and develop effective response strategies.

However, the effectiveness of cyber intelligence applications in times of crisis faces some challenges. The research revealed that the rapidly changing nature of threats and the challenges in data integration can make it difficult to use cyber intelligence effectively. Furthermore, it has been found that the lack of training and knowledge of cybersecurity personnel negatively affects the speed and accuracy of response in crisis situations. These shortcomings can lead to inadequate response to threats and the spread of attacks. Therefore, it was emphasized that in order to increase the effectiveness of cyber intelligence, infrastructures should be constantly updated, personnel training should be strengthened and security protocols should be implemented correctly.

In conclusion, cyber intelligence is critical for early detection and prevention of threats. This research has clearly revealed the necessity of a strong infrastructure, continuous training and coordinated work, as well as the follow-up of technological developments and the harmony of newly developed studies such as machine learning in order to effectively use the data obtained by machine learning in the crisis management processes of cyber intelligence. It has been concluded that cyber intelligence should be applied correctly in order for cyber security teams to access accurate and fast information in times of crisis and for all security units to cooperate effectively. In addition, it has been concluded that in order for cyber intelligence to play a more effective role in cyber security strategies, innovative methods must be continuously adopted and faster adaptation to evolving threats must be achieved.

Discussion

This study discusses the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning in protecting critical infrastructures against cyber threats and providing cyber intelligence, drawing parallels with important studies in the existing literature and supporting the role of cyber intelligence in

protecting critical infrastructures against threats. Genco (2020) stated that the correct implementation of security protocols and personnel training are essential to ensure the security of critical infrastructures. He also highlighted the importance of supporting qualified personnel with appropriate equipment to carry out this process effectively. Our research aligns with these findings, demonstrating that investment in staff training and thorough implementation of safety protocols are key elements in safeguarding critical infrastructure.

Özdemir (2024) pointed out that the rapidly changing nature of cyber threats complicates intelligence processes and emphasized the necessity of implementing innovative methods. Our research concluded that the dynamic nature of threats and challenges in data integration may limit the effectiveness of cyber threat intelligence. To overcome these limitations, infrastructures need to be constantly updated and innovative cybersecurity approaches must be adopted. Forcepoint (2018 akt: Özdemir, 2024) explains that the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning in cyber threat intelligence; It has stated that it offers several advantages, including real-time threat detection, automated incident response, and adaptive defense mechanisms. It was also emphasized that these technologies should be used in a way that is customizable and adaptable to behavioral activities. Our research revealed that these technologies can accelerate response processes and reduce the impact of threats by increasing coordination between security teams, especially in times of crisis. In conclusion, this study aligns with both existing knowledge in the literature and practical needs. It has been clearly demonstrated that cyber threat intelligence is an indispensable tool in early detection of threats, rapid response, and prevention of large-scale damages. It has been concluded that future studies should aim to further implement artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies, make personnel training continuous and develop strong cyber security infrastructures.

Recommendations

Recommendations for the research are given below:

To increase the effectiveness of cyber intelligence in the face of cyber threats, it is necessary to regularly update intelligence infrastructures and adapt to new threats.

Regular training and awareness-raising programs should be implemented to enable cyber security teams to respond quickly and effectively in crisis situations.

In times of crisis, the effective communication and coordinated action of all security units plays an important role in preventing threats.

The integration and rapid analysis of information from different data sources are critical in early detection of threats and making the right decisions.

New technologies need to be integrated into cybersecurity infrastructures in order to respond more quickly and effectively to threats to critical infrastructures.

Artificial intelligence and automation technologies should play a more effective role in crisis management by accelerating the detection and response processes of cyber threats.

Organizations should regularly conduct cybersecurity simulations to test potential crisis scenarios and improve teams' ability to handle such situations.

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